

First records of beetles (Insecta: Coleoptera) for the fauna of Bulgaria from the Belasitsa Mountain

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GUÉORGUIEV B. 2012. First records of beetles (Insecta: Coleoptera) for the fauna of Bulgaria from the Belasitsa Mountain. – *Historia naturalis bulgarica*, **20**: 75-78.

Abstract. *Catops kirbyi* (Leiodidae), *Benibotarus taygetanus* (Lycidae), *Lymexylon navale* (Lymexylidae), *Symbiotes gibberosus* (Endomychidae), *Hypulus bifasciatus* (Melandryidae), *Bolitophagus interruptus* and *Mycetochara humeralis* (Tenebrionidae), three genera (*Benibotarus*, *Lymexylon*, and *Symbiotes*), and subfamily Lymexylinae are reported for the first time from Bulgaria.

Key words: Coleoptera, new records, Bulgaria

Introduction

Identifying material of Coleoptera in order to assess the local biodiversity of the Belasitsa Mountain for two research projects, I found taxa which till now were unrecorded for the fauna of Bulgaria. As the new findings could improve our knowledge on a regional scale, I would like to announce these data.

Material and methods

Localities P2 - P13 are situated south of the Petrich Town, between the Luda Mara River in the east and road Petrich Town – Kongura Chalet in the west. Locality P1 is situated in the Podgorie Area, below the Samuilovo Village, on the left side of the small river of Kolarovska. Data about the GPS coordinates, altitudes and habitats of each locality are represented in Table 1. All the material in P2 – P13 was collected in pitfall traps. The specimens in P1 were caught by hand collecting.

All the material examined is housed in the entomological collection of the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia.

List of species

Leiodidae

Catops kirbyi (Spence, 1815)

Material studied. P3 (17.V-3.VII.2010, 1 specimen); P6 (17.V-3.VII.2010, 1 specimen).
Notes. New species for the fauna of Bulgaria.

Lycidae

Benibotarus taygetanus (Pic, 1905)

Material studied. P11 (24.VIII-6.X.2010, 1 specimen); P13 (5.VII-25.VIII.2010, 2 specimens).

Notes. First findings of the species and genus *Benibotarus* Kôno, 1932 from Bulgaria.

Lymexylidae

Lymexylon navale (Linnaeus, 1758)

Material studied. P6 (17.V-3.VII.2010, 1 specimen).

Notes. First findings of the species, genus *Lymexylon* Fabricius, 1775, and subfamily Lymexylinae Fleming, 1821 from Bulgaria.

Endomychidae

Symbiotes gibberosus (Lucas, 1846)

Material studied. P12 (5.VII-25.VIII.2010, 1 specimen).

Notes. First report of *Symbiotes* L. Redtenbacher, 1849 and *S. gibberosus* from Bulgaria.

Melandryidae

Hypulus bifasciatus (Fabricius, 1792)

Material studied. P2 (18.V-4.VII.2010, 1 specimen); P3 (26.III-17.V.2010, 3 specimens); P4 (18.V-4.VII.2010, 1 specimen); P5 (26.III-17.V.2010, 6 specimens / 17.V-3.VII.2010, 2 specimens); P6 (26.III-17.V.2010, 1 specimen); P7 (29.III-19.V.2010, 1 specimen); P8 (27.III-18.V.2010, 1 specimen); P9 (27.III-18.V.2010, 2 specimens); P10 (27.III-18.V.2010, 3 specimens); P12 (29.III-19.V.2010, 1 specimen / 19.V-5.VII.2010, 1 specimen).

Notes. New species for the fauna of Bulgaria. In contrast to all other species in this list, *H. bifasciatus* seems to be a not infrequent species.

Tenebrionidae

Bolitophagus interruptus Illiger, 1800

Material studied. P1 (on *Polyporus* sp. attached on plane-tree trunk, 9.VIII.2009, 16 specimens).

Notes. New species for the fauna of Bulgaria.

Mycetochara humeralis (Fabricius, 1787)

Material studied. P2 (18.V-4.VII.2010, 1 specimen); P10 (18.V-4.VII.2010, 1 specimen).

Notes. New species for the fauna of Bulgaria.

Table 1.
Data about GPS coordinates, altitudes and habitats of the localities.

Points	GPS coordinates	altitude	Habitat
P1	41.37966N, 23.10316E	340 m	fragmentary old riverside forest of <i>Platanus orientalis</i> L.
P2	41.36326N, 23.201251E	800 m	forest of <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.
P3	41.36561N, 23.204102E	600 m	forest of <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.
P4	41.36775N, 23.200989E	700 m	forest of <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.
P5	41.37225N, 23.200727E	600 m	forest of <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.
P6	41.37459N, 23.203579E	500 m	forest of <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.
P7	41.36356N, 23.210198E	800 m	forest of <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.
P8	41.35437N, 23.204756E	750 m	forest of <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.
P9	41.35203N, 23.201905E	800 m	forest of <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.
P10	41.35212N, 23.204887E	800 m	forest of <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.
P11	41.35672N, 23.207607E	750 m	forest of <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.
P12	41.36131N, 23.210329E	800 m	forest of <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.
P13	41.37245N, 23.206693E	500 m	forest of <i>Castanea sativa</i> Mill.

Acknowledgements

This report represents partial result from work on two research projects: BG 0031 – EEA FM “State and prospects of the *Castanea sativa* population in Belasitsa mountain: climate change adaptation, maintenance of biodiversity and sustainable ecosystem management” of the European Economic Area (EEA) and Norway Grants; National Science Fund grant “ΔO02-176/2008” of the Bulgarian Ministry of Education and Science.

Received: 13.04.2011

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**Първи находки на твърдокрили насекоми (Insecta: Coleoptera)
за фауната на България от Беласица планина**

Борислав ГЕОРГИЕВ

(Резюме)

Съобщават се седем нови вида от Coleoptera за фауната на България от Беласица планина: *Catops kirbyi* (Leiodidae), *Benibotarus taygetanus* (Lycidae), *Lymexylon navale* (Lymexylidae), *Symbiotes gibberosus* (Endomychidae), *Hypulus bifasciatus* (Melandryidae), *Bolitophagus interruptus* и *Mycetochara humeralis* (Tenebrionidae). Нови таксони за фауната на страната са също и родове *Benibotarus*, *Lymexylon* и *Symbiotes*, както и подсемейство Lymexylineae.